

**INFLUENCE OF HANDS-ON-ACTIVITIES ON ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE
OF BIOLOGY STUDENTS IN OSUN STATE SENIOR SECONDARY SCHOOLS**

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Abstract

The study examined the influence of Hands-on-Activities on the academic performance of Biology students in Osun State Senior Secondary Schools. One hundred and eighty (180) Biology students selected randomly from public secondary schools in Osun State participated in the study. The study used pretest, posttest control group non-randomized quasi-experimental research design. Two instructional packages were developed: one for the treatment group and the other was subjected to the traditional method of teaching. The Biology Achievement Test was used for data collection. Data were analyzed using mean and standard deviation to answer the research questions while the analysis of co-variance and t-test were used to test the hypotheses summary of the results revealed that the instructional Hands-on-Activities method was more effective than the traditional method in enhancing academic performance of male and female students in Biology. The researcher concluded that the Hands-on-Activities technique is a more effective teaching method for teaching Biology. Because of this, it is hereby recommended that Hands-on-Activities for teaching and learning Biology should be given due consideration irrespective of the gender of the students in the school.

Introduction

Biology as the science of life is offered in all senior secondary schools in Nigeria. It attracts the patronage of both science-oriented and art-based students. Learning Biology equips students with knowledge and skills that help them to face challenges in society especially those related to common diseases, pollution and genetics (Mwe da and Ndavenbye, 2021) to build a progressive society (Agboghroma and Oyovwi 2015). Cherosol et al, (2021) pointed out that teaching Biology is important because it equips the students to comprehend the world around them or skills and equips them with the necessary skills to build a progressive society (Agbonghroma and Oyovwi, 2015). There is no gain saying about the fact that Biology occupies a very sensitive position in medical science and related disciplines. This informs several efforts geared towards studying Biology at a secondary school level of education (Akinfe et al 2012).

The broad aim and expectations of any teaching and learning programme are productivity and positively evaluated end-product (achievement) but in recent times observations in students' academic performance in science generally, and Biology in particular over the years in the result of Senior Secondary Certificate Examination (SSCE) conducted by West African Examination Council WAEC and National Examination Council (NECO) revealed that a few numbers of students perform better in Biology examination compared with other subjects (Adodo & Oyeniya 2013).

Despite efforts through research on strategies to improve performance in Biology, researchers' reports and the WAEC chief examiners' annual reports have continued to highlight students' weaknesses in answering questions related to difficult concepts in areas such as Genetics, Ecology and Evolution (Mweda and Ndayenbye, 2021). Such weaknesses continue to induce student's inability to comprehend or represent concepts in table's graphs and diagrams, these repeated reports of constant poor performance in SSCE Biology have attracted a lot of concern from science educators. Thus, research in science education in Nigeria has continued to seek better ways of teaching Biology to maximize meaningful learning and to identify caused variables for the repeated failures in examinations at the SSCE (Etobro and Fabinu, 2017). To avert this, Hands-on-Activities as a teaching strategy have been well emphasized as a method that can enhance performance in Biology and other related subjects.

Some researchers have indicated that the scaffolding teaching approach is an effective teaching technique in modern-day teaching because students taught using the approach demonstrated a higher academic achievement than those taught using the traditional approach. Hence the present study was designated to find out the effects of the scaffolding approach on senior secondary school students' achievement in Biology in Osun State to find out the extent to which Hands-on-Activities teaching strategy would be effective in the teaching of Biology in secondary schools.

In recent years, educators have advocated a paradigm shift from passive sitting and listening to a more active and dynamic learning experience in many developed countries, a decline in students' interest in science and the recruitment of students to science studies has been noticed (UNESCO, 2013). The decline in interest applies not only to hard science subjects such as Physics and Chemistry, students' interest in Biology also tends to decrease in Primary to Secondary School (Lowe, 1992).

To counteract the existing decline in interest and to motivate adolescents to pursue science in higher education, it is important to investigate situational factors that might spark or hold students' interest in scientific topics as well as their interest in working scientifically. The need for concrete experiences in science instruction is advocated because they enhance students' learning and provide a more authentic view of science. Acquiring information, developing methods of thinking, applying science principles and forming attitudes are general categories of objectives related to science learning. Researchers advocate that creativity and higher-order learning may be achieved by the use of Hands-on-Activities. Activities that provide students with the opportunity to switch over freely and continuously between collecting processing and interpreting the data may prove fruitful and effective for better learning (Hussain and Akhtar, 2013).

Hands-on-Learning or experimental learning has become a common phase in science education. Hands-on-Learning is learning by doing. It combines active learning

with concrete experiences, abstract concepts and reflections to engage all learning styles. Hands-on-Learning involves the learner in total learning experiences which enhances the learner's ability to think critically. The learner must plan a process to test a hypothesis and put the process into motion using various hands-on materials. See the process into completion and be able to explain the attained results. Hands-on-Learning enables students to become critical thinkers, able to apply not only what they learned but more importantly the process of learning to various life situations.

In general, conducting hands-on- activities in Biology classes, for example in the field of laboratory settings is widely recommended by educational authorities like the National Association of Biology Teachers (NABT, 2012) Most empirical studies provide evidence for the assumption that eradicating hands-on- activities leads to motivational outcomes For instance (Gisol, 2023) asked teachers and students to distinguish what makes Biology classes motivating.

Studies carried out as claimed by some researchers (Louca and Zacharia,2012) have indicated that an effective teaching approach is an effective teaching technique in modern-day teaching because students taught with an activities teaching approach demonstrated a higher academic achievement than those taught with a traditional approach: Hence the present study

Aims and Objectives of the Study

The major purpose of the study is to ascertain the effect of the Hands-on-Activities teaching method on the academic performance of Biology students in Senior Secondary Schools in Osun State. Specifically, the study objectives were to:

- (a) expose students to Hands-on-Activities method of teaching in Biology
- (b) expose male and female students to the Hands-on-Activities method of teaching in Biology.

Research Questions

This study was guided by the following research questions

- a) What is the academic performance of students exposed to the traditional method and those exposed to the Hands-on-Activities method of teaching in Biology?
- b) What is the academic performance of male and female students exposed to the Hands-on-Activities method of teaching in Biology?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at a 0.05 level of significance

- i. There is no significant difference between the academic performance of students exposed to traditional methods and those exposed to the Hands-on-Activities method of teaching in Biology.
- ii. There is no significant difference between the academic performance of male and female students exposed to the Hands-on-Activities method of teaching in Biology.

Research Design

The study used a pre-test, post-test, control group, and non-randomized quest experimental research design:

Experimental Group	Pretest	Treatment	Posttest
	Q1	X1	Q2
Control group	Q1	X2	Q2

Where

- Q1 - pretest for both groups before treatment
- X1- Hands-on-Activities
- X2- traditional method
- Q2- Post-test for both groups after treatment

The experimental and control groups were used and there was no randomization of the subjects hence intact classes were used.

Population of the Study

The population used for the study was one hundred and eighty students of SSII Biology students in Osun State public secondary schools.

Instrumentation

The instrument that was used for the data collection was the Biology Achievement test (BAT) which was made up of questions from the SSII syllabus on Biology. The instrument was made up of fifty (50) standardized SSCE, NECO multiple choice test, items, with options A to D the question covered topics on the classification of plants organization of life, plant and animal nutrition.

There was no validity for the instrument because it is a standardized instrument reliability test was not also conducted. After all, a standardized test was employed. At the onset of the experiment, the Biology Achievement Test was administered to both the treatment and control groups as a pretest. This was performed by the subject teachers the subject teachers were trained by the researcher for a week before the experimental period to equip them with skills and knowledge that will enable them to implement Hands-on-Activities and methods of teaching during the experimental period. At the end of the test, the question paper and answer scripts were collected from the students.

The same instrument was administered to the students at the end of the experimental period which was six (6) weeks. These serve as post-tests. The experimental procedure was carried out thus; two instructional packages were developed by the researcher.

The first package was based on the Hands-on-Activities method while the second package was based on the traditional method. The questions were drawn from the same scheme of work. At the beginning of the experiment, the subjects in both treatment and control groups were given the pretest, after the test the regular Biology teachers began the experiment in their respective schools ensuring that they followed the lesson procedure developed from the instructional package during the pre-experimental training. The treatment groups were taught using the instructional package for the experimental group while the control groups were taught using the instructional package for the control

group. The experiment covered six (6) weeks according to the school timetable. The post-test was admitted to the subjects in the two groups at the end of the experiment.

Data collected were analyzed using the mean and standard deviation to answer the research questions, while the analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) was used to test hypothesis one, and the t-test was used to test hypothesis two at the probability of 0.05.

Results

Research Question 1. What is the mean academic performance of students exposed to Hands-on-Learning activities, and those not exposed to Hands-on-Learning activities?

Mean performance of experimental and control Group

Groups	N	Mean	Standard Deviation	Mean Difference
Those taught using Hands-on-Activities	90	72.03	7.34	10.88
Those taught without using Hands-on-Activities	90	62.17	10.09	

Table 1 reveals that the mean academic performance of students taught Biology using the Hands-on-Activities method is 72.03 while the mean performance of those taught Biology traditional method was 62.17 the table also reveals that the mean difference in performance between the experiment and control group is 10.88 this indicates that those taught Biology using Hands-on-Activities method performed better than those taught Biology using the traditional method.

Research Question 2. What is the mean academic performance between male and female students exposed to Hands-on-Activities method of teaching in Biology?

Table 2: Mean performance of male and female taught Biology with scaffolding method

Sex	N	Mean	Standard deviation	Mean difference
Male	38	64.61	7.506	0.24
Female	52	68.02	8.24	

Table 2 reveals that the mean academic performance of male students exposed to Biology using Hands-on-Activities method of teaching is 64.61 while the mean academic performance of female students exposed to Biology using the same method is 68.02. The table also reveals that the mean difference in performance between the male and female students is 0.24. This indicates that female students taught Biology employing the Hands-on-Activities method performed better than their male counterparts with 0.24 using the same method.

Testing the Hypotheses

The hypothesis was tested using Analysis of variance ANCOVA for hypothesis 1 and t-test for hypothesis 2 at 0.05 level of significance.

Hypothesis One: There is no significant difference between the academic performance of students exposed to traditional methods and those exposed to Hands-on-Activities methods of teaching in Biology.

Table 3: Analysis of covariance ANCOVA on the performance between experimental and control group

Source	Type III sum of squares	Df	Mean square	F	Sig.
Corrected Model	167729.103 ³	2	8761.102	78.142	.000
Intercept	20653.462	1	20653.462	182.676	.000
Pre-test	621.372	1	621.372	6.092	.012
Group	14360.43	1	14360.43	141.123	.000
Error	16162.122	177	124.822		
Total	644311.002	179			

Table 3 shows that the type III sum of squares for the group is 14360.43 at a degree of freedom of 1 with an F-value of 141.123 is significant at a P-value of .000. Since the p-value is less than probability at 0.05 the null hypothesis is rejected. It means that there is a significant difference between the mean performance of students taught Biology using Hands-on-Activities method of teaching and those taught with traditional methods of teaching.

Hypothesis Two: There is no significant difference between the academic performance of male and female students exposed to Hands-on-Activities methods of teaching in Biology.

Table 4: The t-test of male and female performance of Biology students taught with the scaffolding method

Sex	N	Mean	Standard deviation	Df	t-value	p-value	dec
Male	38	67.82	7.657	88	.0961	.0927	Sig.
Female	52	68.05	8.528		.0912		

Table 4 shows that the t-value of 0.96 at a degree of freedom of 0.88 is not significant at a P-value of 0.12 since the P-value is greater than the alpha value of 0.05 the null hypothesis is accepted. This means that there is no significant difference between the mean academic performance of male and female students exposed to Hands-on-Activities method of teaching in Biology.

Discussion

The result of data analysis indicated that the instructional Hands-on-Activities approach shows little difference in the mean achievement scores of male and female students in Biology. This finding disagrees with the view of Goodpaster, et al (2012) who

observed that male students perform better than female students in mathematics because the subject involves the calculation of figures and since female students are always afraid of Mathematics. The findings of this study equally deviated from the view of Alokun and Arijesuyo (2013) who pointed out that female student in secondary schools performs better in subjects like Biology as opposed to mathematical subjects like accounting.

The finding supports the view of Koko (2016) who stressed that for instructional Hands-on-Activities to be most effective teachers need to balance levels of intellectual challenge and instructional support irrespective of the gender and ability of the students.

On the issue of the effect of gender and instructional approach on students' achievement in Biology, the result of the data analysis in test analysis of gender on student mean achievement in Biology does not show any significant difference. The mean achievement scores are higher for instructional Hands-on-Activities approaches at all levels of gender in the test of significance, the calculated f-values are less than the critical values on the student mean achievement in Biology as shown in the table. Both male and female students performed well after being exposed to treatment effects under the same condition. This means that both males and females benefited equally from the Hands-on-Activities instructional approach. The treatment allowed them to solve problems on their own with little assistance from their teacher, this is in line with the view of Makanjuola Pratt (2000) and Ben Sidiq (2013 (2000) who observed that Hands-on-Activities help to achieve the goal of any educator which is to help students develop skills that will make them self-directed learners.

Recommendations

Irrespective of gender, Hands-on-Activities could be used during Biology lessons. Curriculum planners should adopt Hands-on-Activities as an adequate teaching method for teaching Biology. There should be organized workshops, seminars and symposiums for teachers on the importance of using a hands-on approach in teaching Biology.

Conclusion

From the findings, it could be concluded that the effect of Hands-on-Activities teaching method on the Academic Performance of Biology Secondary School Students in Osun State. Based on the findings, the researcher concluded that the use of Hands-on-Activities in teaching Biology enhances the learning and understanding of Biology topics irrespective of the gender of students. This led to a significance difference in the means scores of male and female students taught using Hands-on-Activities approach than those taught with conventional methods.

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